

“A SINGLE ARM CLINICAL TRIAL TO EVALUATE THE EFFICACY OF BRAHMIGHRITA IN PREMENSTRUAL SYNDROME”

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ABSTRACT

Premenstrual Syndrome (PMS) is a psychoneuroendocrine disorder marked by cyclic emotional, behavioural and physical symptoms during the luteal phase, resolving with menstruation. It affects many women of reproductive age due to hormonal fluctuations, altered serotonin and GABA activity and individual sensitivity. Common symptoms include irritability, mood swings, anxiety, breast tenderness, bloating and fatigue. PMS is not mentioned in Ayurveda directly but can be correlated with *Pitta Prakopa* with *Vata Sanchya Awastha* is *Rituvyateeta kala* symptomatically. *Brahmighrita* with its *Medhya* and *Rasayana* properties promotes mental calmness and emotional stability. Ingredients like *Trikatu*, *Danti*, *Aragwadha* and *Vidanga* alleviate somatic symptoms through *Doshaghna* action offering holistic relief. *Bacosides* in *Brahmi* modulate serotonergic and dopaminergic pathways. Overall *Brahmighrita* exhibits *Tridoshaghna*, *Vedanasthapana*, *Balya* and *Medhya* properties, making it beneficial in PMS

management.

KEYWORDS: Premenstrual syndrome, *Brahmighrita*, *Rituvyateeta Kala*.

INTRODUCTION

Premenstrual Syndrome is a recurring set of physical, behavioural and psychological symptoms appearing during the luteal phase of the menstrual cycle and subsiding with menstruation.^[1] Globally the prevalence of PMS is significant, with estimates ranging between 24 - 48% of women of reproductive age.^[2] While recognized clinically since the early 20th century PMS remains a diagnosis based on symptom patterns rather than laboratory findings and modern treatments focus mainly on symptomatic relief through hormonal therapy, analgesics or antidepressants.

In Ayurveda, PMS can be correlated with the *Rituvyateeta Kala* phase of the menstrual cycle characterized by *Pitta* predominance and *Vata Sanchaya Awastha*, making it a *Tridoṣhaja* condition.^[3] Improper lifestyle and dietary habits during this stage are believed to trigger symptoms. *Brahmighṛita* described in *Aṣṭanga Hṛidaya Uttara Tantra*.^[4] is traditionally indicated for *Manasa Vikara* and *Vandhyatva*. Its ingredients are *Brahmi*, *Sankhapuṣpi*, *Trivṛitta*, *Sunṭhi* and *Trikatu* collectively exert *Medhya Rasayana*, *Tridoṣhahara* and *Vedanasthapana* actions. These properties help to balance the Hypothalamo–Pituitary–Ovarian axis, enhance mood stability, reduce pain and improve cognitive and emotional resilience. The *Ghṛita* base improves bioavailability and adds neuroprotective and nutritive benefits.^[5]

Thus *Brahmighṛita* offers a holistic Ayurvedic approach for PMS management by addressing both physiological and psychological aspects through *Dosha* balance, mental calmness and enhanced overall well-being.

AIM AND OBJECTIVES

AIM: To evaluate the efficacy of *Brahmighṛita* in management of Premenstrual syndrome.

OBJECTIVE: To evaluate the efficacy of *Brahmighṛita* on associated symptoms of Premenstrual syndrome.

HYPOTHESIS

H0- There is statistically significant effect of *Brahmighṛita* in management of Premenstrual syndrome.

H1- There is statistically no significant effect of *Brahmighṛita* in management of Premenstrual syndrome.

METHODOLOGY

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A comprehensive theoretical and systematic evaluation of the research methodology is crucial before initiating any planned study to prevent possible errors or inaccuracies. The present clinical study titled “A SINGLE ARM CLINICAL TRIAL TO EVALUATE THE EFFICACY OF *BRAHMI GHRITA* IN PREMENSTRUAL SYNDROME” was conducted on 30 patients who were randomly selected from the OPD of Prasuti Tantra and Stri Roga Alva’s Ayurveda Medical College as well as from other referral sources.

METHOD OF COLLECTION OF DATA

STUDY DESIGN- Interventional single group study.

SAMPLE SIZE- 30 patients suffering from PMS and fulfilling the inclusion criteria were selected for the study.

DIAGNOSTIC CRITERIA

Patients fulfilling the following diagnostic criteria were selected for the study:

1. Symptoms consistent to PMS were confirmed by PMS scale.
2. Symptoms appear reproducibly during 2 cycles of prospective recordings.
3. Symptoms remit shortly after onset of menses.
4. Symptoms are restricted to the luteal phase of the menstrual cycle.
5. Symptoms present in absence of any pharmacologic therapy, hormone ingestion, drug or alcohol abuse, diagnosed psychiatric and metabolic disorders.

INCLUSION CRITERIA

1. Patient fulfilling diagnostic criteria.
2. Women in age group 16-40 years, not using any hormonal contraceptive.
3. Women having regular menstrual cycle.
4. Based on PMS Scale screening score.

EXCLUSION CRITERIA

1. Patient with diagnosed case of psychiatric disorder i.e neurodevelopment disorder, Schizophrenia etc.
2. Patient diagnosed with any pelvic pathology like endometriosis, inflammatory disease.

3. Systemic disorders like chronic renal diseases, cardiac disorders, tuberculosis, hypertension, diabetes, thyroid dysfunctions.
4. Patient with Premenstrual Dysphoric Disorder.
5. Females using oral contraceptive pills, IUCD, injectable contraceptives.

INTERVENTION

- Patients fulfilling the diagnostic criteria according to PMS Scale, were given treatment.
- Duration of treatment was 2 consecutive menstrual cycle and 1 cycle follow up without medicine.
- *Brahmighrita* in the dose 15 ml BD was given with *Sukhoshnajala* 7 days prior to menstruation.

ASSESSMENT CRITERIA

A. SUBJECTIVE CRITERIA- Symptoms appear during 7 days prior to menstrual cycle.

B. OBJECTIVE CRITERIA- Symptomatic analysis based on PMS scale screening.

PMS SCALE

Table No. 1.

Sr No	Symptom	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Very Often	Always
1	Breast tenderness and swelling					
2	Abdominal bloating					
3	Weight gain					
4	Headache					
5	Dizziness / Fainting					
6	Fatigue					
7	Palpitation					
8	Pelvic discomfort and pain					
9	Abdominal cramp					
10	Increased appetite					
11	Change in bowel habit					
12	Generalised ache and pain					
13	Food cravings(sugar / salt)					
14	Skin changes, rashes, pimples					
15	Nausea/ Vomiting					
16	Muscle and joint pain					
17	Irritability					
18	Anxiety					
19	Tension					
20	Mood swing					
21	Loss of concentration					
22	Depression					
23	Easy crying / Crying spell					

24	Sleep changes					
25	Confusion					
26	Aggression					
27	Hopelessness					
28	Forgetfulness					
29	Social withdrawal					
30	Restlessness					
31	Lack of self-control					
32	Feeling guilty					
33	Clumsiness					
34	Lack of interest in usual activities					
35	Poor judgement					
36	Impaired work performance					
37	Obsessional thought					
38	Compulsive behaviour					
39	Irritated thought					
40	Being over sensitive					

ASSESSMENT CRITERIA

Table No. 2.

Level of Symptoms		Actual Score	Percentage score
No symptoms		1-40	<20%
Mild	Only slightly apparent	41- 80	21-40%
Moderate	Aware of symptom, but doesn't affect daily activity	81-120	41-60%
Severe	Continuously bothered by symptoms	121-160	61-80%
Very Severe	Interferes with daily activity	161-180	>80%

ASSESSMENT TIME

Assessment was done on second day of onset of each menstrual cycle for 2 consecutive cycles.

FOLLOW UP

Second day of third menstrual cycle.

DISCUSSION

A. DISCUSSION ON DISEASE REVIEW

Premenstrual Syndrome (PMS) is a multifactorial condition characterized by mood, behavioural, and physical symptoms occurring during the luteal phase of the menstrual cycle and subsiding with menstruation. Its exact cause is uncertain, but contributing factors include hormonal fluctuations, neurochemical sensitivity, genetics, psychosocial stress, and lifestyle influences. Diagnosis (as per WHO–ICD-10) requires at least one mood or physical symptom

in the premenstrual phase, commonly assessed using the Premenstrual Syndrome Scale (PMSS).^[6] Management is symptomatic focusing on stress reduction, cognitive behavioural therapy and pharmacological support when necessary, aiming to reduce symptom burden and improve daily functioning with lifestyle modification.

In Ayurveda, PMS corresponds to *Ritu Vyateeta Kala* where *Pitta* predominance and *Vata Sanchaya* cause physical and psychological disturbances. *Aharaja*, *Viharaja*, *Manasika* and *Beejadushti* factors act as causative agents.^[7,8,9] In individuals with *Heena Prakriti* these factors aggravate *Vata-Pitta Doshas*, producing symptoms similar to PMS.

B. DISCUSSION ON OBSERVATION

AGE:- Among the 30 participants enrolled in the study, 40% belonged to the 16–23 year age group, 47% were between 24–31 years and 13% were in the 32–40 year category. The predominance of cases in the 24–31 year group may be attributed to active reproductive hormonal activity along with academic and professional stress. These findings suggest a higher prevalence of PMS among younger women.

OCCUPATION:- Among the 30 participants, 23% were housewives, 27% were employed and 50% were students. The predominance of PMS among students may be attributed to learning stress, competitive pressure and irregular dietary habits. This observation suggests that a stressful lifestyle could be a major contributory factor in the development of PMS.

MARITAL STATUS:- Among the 30 participants, 40% were married while 60% were unmarried. The majority of the study population thus comprised unmarried women.

DURATION OF SYMPTOM:- Among the 30 subjects, 77% experienced PMS symptoms lasting up to 7 days, while 34% reported symptoms persisting for 8–14 days. The prominence of symptoms towards the end of the cycle can be explained by declining estrogen and rising progesterone levels, supporting the hormonal basis of the syndrome.

FAMILY HISTORY:- Among the 30 patients studied, 40% reported a positive family history of PMS, while 60% did not. This indicates that, in addition to genetic predisposition, hormonal, social, and psychological factors also play a significant role in the aetiology of PMS.

PMSS SCORING:- Among the 30 patients, 20% exhibited mild PMS scores, 63% had moderate scores, and 17% presented with severe scores.

ROUTINE WORK AFFECTED:- Among the 30 patients, routine work was unaffected in 67%, moderately affected in 27%, and severely affected in 6%. The study indicates that women with moderate to severe PMS scores experienced regular interference with daily activities due to persistent symptoms.

RELIGION:- Among 30 patients, 83% patients were Hindu, indicating predominance of Hindu Population in given data.

SOCIOECONOMIC STATUS:- 63% population was in the middle class **PRAKRITI :-** Among the 30 patients, 37% had *Vata–Pitta Prakriti*, 27% were *Vata–Kapha*, 23% were *Pitta–Kapha*, and 13% exhibited *Vata–Pitta–Kapha* constitution. Since the pathophysiology of PMS is linked to *Vata Sanchaya* and *Pitta Prakopa* during the *Rituvyateeta* period, individuals with *Vata–Pitta Prakriti* appear to be more vulnerable.

DIET :- Among the 30 patients, 67% reported consuming a mixed diet. The predominance of mixed dietary habits suggests that diet may influence PMS symptoms, with non vegetarian intake potentially contributing to greater symptom severity due to effects on fat and hormone metabolism.

SLEEP:- Among the 30 patients, 40% reported reduced sleep, 37% experienced disturbed sleep, and 23% had sound sleep. The study indicates a strong correlation between PMS and disturbances in neurotransmitter balance.

C. DISCUSSION ON RESULTS

PHYSIOLOGICAL SYMPTOMS

The mean somatic symptom score decreased from 46.87 to 37.27 after treatment, showing a 20.5% improvement, with a slight relapse at follow-up (37.10). The median score reduced from 48.5 to 36, a highly significant change ($p < 0.001$). Clinically, patients reported relief from headache, breast tenderness, abdominal bloating, and body ache, attributed to the antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, *Balya* and *Rasayana* properties of *Brahmi* and *Goghrita*.

PSYCHOLOGICAL SYMPTOMS

The mean psychological symptom score decreased from 35.57 to 25.50 after treatment, showing a 28.3% improvement, which was sustained at follow-up. The median score reduced from 35.5 to 26, a highly significant change ($p < 0.001$). Clinically, this reflected relief from anxiety, irritability, mood swings, and tension, attributed to *Brahmi's* modulation of serotonergic and dopaminergic activity and its *Medhya* properties promoting psychological balance.

BEHAVIOURAL SYMPTOMS

The mean behavioural symptom score decreased from 28.67 to 22.22 after treatment, showing a 22.6% improvement, and remained stable at follow-up (22.43). The median score reduced from 25.5 to 21, a highly significant change ($p < 0.001$). Clinically, this reflected better social interaction, fewer anger outbursts, and improved daily functioning, attributed to *Brahmi's* anxiolytic, antidepressant, and *Medhya* properties.

OVERALL EFFECT

The mean PMS score decreased from 111.1 to 84.8 after treatment, showing a 23.6% improvement, with a slight increase at follow-up (85.5) but still lower than baseline. The median score reduced from 109.5 to 84.5, a highly significant change ($p < 0.001$). These findings confirm that *Brahmighrita* effectively reduces the severity of Premenstrual Syndrome.

EFFECT DURING FOLLOW UP

Following the 60-day treatment period, therapy was stopped and patients were observed for another month to evaluate recurrence of PMS symptoms. Physiological scores showed a minimal decrease from 37.267 to 37.110. Psychological parameters remained unchanged at 25.500, while behavioural symptoms increased slightly from 22.200 to 22.433. As a result, the total PMSS score, which had previously fallen to 84.80, increased modestly to 85.50 in the follow-up. Despite this rise, symptom severity was still lower than before treatment. The slight increment in values could reflect stress arising from routine lifestyle factors.

PROBABLE MODE OF ACTION OF *BRAHMIGHRITA*

In the present study, *Brahmighrita* was selected as the therapeutic intervention. *Ghrita* based formulations are considered ideal for managing psychosomatic disorders due to their ability to cross the blood–brain barrier and enhance drug delivery.

1. BASED ON RASAPANCHAKA

Brahmi with *Tikta–Kashaya Rasa*, *Sheeta Virya* and *Madhura Vipaka* pacifies *Pitta* and *Vata Dosh*. Its *Medhya* and *Rasayana* qualities calm the mind, improve emotional balance and reduce irritability, mood swings, and anxiety seen in PMS.^[10] *Trikatu* (*Sunthi*, *Maricha*, *Pippali*), being *Katu Rasa*, *Ushna Virya*, and *Deepana Pachana*, corrects *Agnimandya* and *Ama* formation, which are often linked with bloating, heaviness, and indigestion during PMS.^[11,12,13] It also acts as a bioenhancer for *Brahmi*, improving its CNS effect.

Sankhapushpi with *Tikta Rasa* and *Medhya Karma* directly supports psychological and behavioural symptom relief, reducing stress and irritability.^[14] Thus, the formulation provides a balanced effect on all three *Doshas*, with a specific emphasis on pacifying *Vata* and *Pitta*, the key *Doshas* in PMS pathophysiology.

2. BASED ON KARMA

Brahmi, *Sankhapushpi*:–*Medhya* and *Rasayana Karma* - Improve mental clarity, reduce irritability, depression, and mood swings, enhancing overall emotional stability. *Trivrita*, *Danti*, *Saptala*: –*Vedanasthapana* and *Shoolahara Karma*: Relieve lower abdominal cramps, pelvic pain, and headache associated with PMS.^[15,16,17]

Saptala, *Danti*:–*Shothahara Karma*: Reduce inflammatory changes, oedema, and breast tenderness.

Vidanga :-*Krimighna Karma*: Helps maintain gut health, reducing digestive discomfort that often aggravates PMS symptoms.^[18]

Trivrita, *Danti*, *Aragwadha*, *Saptala* :- *Deepana*, *Pachana*, *Rechana* and *Sramsana karma* : Help in clearing *Srotorodha*, supporting *Apana Vayu* function, and relieving abdominal congestion, constipation, and pelvic heaviness commonly experienced in PMS.

3. BASED ON PHARMACODYNAMIC PROFILE

Neuroprotective and anti-stress effect: -*Brahmi* and *Sankhapushpi* exert adaptogenic effects by modulating serotonergic and noradrenergic pathways, thereby reducing anxiety, irritability, and sleep disturbances in PMS.^[19,20]

Phytoestrogenic influence:-Certain components support hormonal regulation, balancing estrogen–progesterone interplay which underlies PMS symptoms.

Anti-inflammatory and analgesic:- Ingredients like *Trivrita*, *Danti*, and *Sunthi* reduce pain, cramps, abdominal cramps and inflammatory changes *Ghrita* in modern terms is a rich source of essential fatty acids, fat-soluble vitamins (A, D, E, K), and acts as a lipid-based drug delivery system enhancing the bioavailability of phytochemicals from *Brahmi*. Its neurotropic and calming effects complement *Brahmi*'s nootropic activity.

CONCLUSION

The above study i.e “A SINGLE ARM CLINICAL TRIAL TO EVALUATE THE EFFICACY OF *BRAHMIGHRITA* IN PREMENSTRUAL SYNDROME” conclude that *Brahmighrita* by its holistic approach showed statistically significant effect in the management of premenstrual syndrome. Thus alternate hypothesis is accepted and null hypothesis is rejected.

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